

PREDICTION OF THE CREEP-RUPTURE LIFETIME FOR SOME COMPOSITE MATRICES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

ALEKSANDRS MALMEISTERS

Institute of Polymer Mechanics Latvian Academy of Sciences

23, Aizkraukles st. Riga, LV-1006, LATVIA

ABSTRACT

Results of an experimental study of predicting the dependence of the creep-rupture lifetime on the load level and temperature are presented. Polycarbonate and hardened epoxy binder EDT-10 representing thermoplastic and thermosetting polymers employed for preparing various reinforced plastics were objects of the research. Long-term stress strength curves were computed for these materials from relationships, using the parameters of deformation rules determined from short-time creep experiments at elevated temperatures, as well as basing on the criterion of constancy of time of ultimate stress work-at-break connected with the temperature according to the Arrhenius law.

Keywords: predicting, long-term strength, creep, temperature-time analogy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since data accumulation on the long-term strength of materials in definite service conditions is greatly a labour-consuming process, the development of new methods and verification of the suitability of the existing ones for predicting strain-strength characteristics of materials in long-term loading and at elevated temperatures become quite a pressing problem.

Using investigations on hardened epoxy binder EDT-10 and polycarbonate Dilon, a method is proposed for an accelerated evaluation of long-term strength in creep by analysing the deformation data obtained in short term tests at various levels of elevated temperatures. A material subjected to ultimate loading may undergo elastic, viscoelastic and plastic deformation, as well as the process of gradual failure or damage accumulation. The present method is based on hypothesis that the failure of a material is the result of an accumulated process of deformation, and, consequently

the use of a respective strength criterion applied to strain curves allows us to predict the time prior to failure. In other words, prediction of the long-term strength requires that a law of long-term deformation including all its parameters and expressed as mathematical expressions should be defined and solved in terms of ultimate stresses with regard to a certain strength criterion representing ultimate strain-strength characteristics of a definite material. The defined law of long-term strength will imply finding the necessary parameters and time functions by applying the temperature-time analogy (TTA) to the analysis of the data of accelerated creep tests at elevated temperatures, as is given in [1].

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is commonly known that the mechanical properties of many polymeric materials are dependent upon the duration, rate and level of applied loads and are sensitive to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity. Thus, a growth of the load rate calls forth an increase in ultimate stress σ^R and a decrease in ultimate

Table 1

Figure 1. Dependence of the ultimate stress work-at-break W^R on temperature.

Notes. W_e^R - calculated test data; W_a^R - theoretical data - eq. 1.

strain ϵ^R , and vice versa. This circumstance lies at the basis of the strength criterion assumed in [2,3] and which defines that failure of a material takes place, whenever the stress work W reaches a critical value W^R . In this case W^R is a rheological characteristic of the polymeric binder and is expressed by an area below the $\sigma-\epsilon$ diagram at the moment of failure. The loading of a material under various thermal conditions makes it necessary to determine how strongly in failure the critical value W^R is associated with the temperature. To this purpose, the materials were subjected to a quasi-static mode of loading with $\dot{\sigma}_{11} = 5$ MPa/min and at constant levels of 20, 40, 60 and 80 °C. An analysis of the data obtained from averaged stress-strain diagrams

for each temperature by the numerical integration method is given in Table 1 and in Figure 1.

It is seen from Figure 1 that the calculated values of W_c^R of both materials can be well approximated by the method of the least squares using the Arrhenius law as follows:

$$W_a^R(T) = C \exp(\alpha/T) , \quad (1)$$

where T is the Kelvin temperature. The characteristics obtained for the polycarbonate and EDT-10 were $C = 0.675 \text{ MPa}$; $\alpha = 344.4 \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $C = 2.255 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ MPa}$; $\alpha = 1.947 \cdot 10^3 \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively.

When total deformation is expressed by $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_c$, where ε_0 is an elastic component and ε_c a creep deformation, a dependence of the stress work-at-break can be written in the form:

$$W^R(T) = \frac{\sigma \varepsilon_0}{2} + \sigma \varepsilon_c(t, T) \quad (2)$$

Here the right-side part contains an equation for determination of the material, which is suggested to be given for both materials in the following general form:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(t, T) = \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{2G} + \frac{\sigma_{ii}}{K} \delta_{ij} + \int_0^t K(t-s, T) \frac{\partial R}{\partial \sigma_{ij}}(s) ds ;$$

$$R = c_1 I_1^2 + c_2 I_2 + c_3 (c_1 I_1^2 + c_2 I_2)^2 , \quad (3)$$

where R is some function of the first I_1 and the second I_2 invariant of the stress tensor; G a shear modulus; K a volume elasticity modulus and δ_{ij} the Kronecher delta. A function of the creep effect is assumed to be a sum of exponents, and, using the TTA principle and after integration, we obtain

$$F_c = K(t-s, T) ds = \sum_{i=1}^n L_i (1 - \exp(-t a_m / \tau_i)) ;$$

$$\ln a_m = c_m (t - T_0) ; T_0 = 20^0 . C \quad (4)$$

It is not difficult respectively to show that, after some transformations, Eq.(3) can be written for creep in tension and shear as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{11}(t, T) = \frac{\sigma_{11}}{E} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{E} + \frac{c_3 \sigma_{11}^3}{E^2} \right) F_c(t, T) ;$$

$$\varepsilon_{12}(t, T) = \frac{\sigma_{12}}{2G} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{2G} + \frac{c_3 \sigma_{12}^3}{2G^2} \right) F_c(t, T) , \quad (5)$$

where the time and temperature function $F_c(t, T)$ in the form of Eq.(4) is assumed to be independent of the stress state type and is common for linear and nonlinear components of the total creep deformation. These assumptions have been confirmed in [4], wherein the necessary characteristics of the thermal viscoelasticity of binder EDT-10 were obtained experimentally and allowed to calculate not only simple, but also complex stress-strain states and to predict the long-term processes of deformation in the nonlinear region of viscoelastic properties of the material. However, the case is far from general. As it will be marked further for the polycarbonate, functions of the temperature-time shift for some materials may differ. This condition acquires a principal importance in describing the processes of deformation preceding to failure, because then the role of nonlinear viscoelastic deformations becomes the decisive.

Figure 2. Creep curves for polycarbonate under shear.

Table 2. Thermorheological characteristics of EDT-10 and polycarbonate.

EDT-10			Polycarbonate			
i	L_i	τ_i	i	L_{li}	$L_{\beta}, \text{MPa}^{-1}$	τ_i, sec
1	0.061	50	1	0.079	0.198	20
2	0.053	$2.2 \cdot 10^4$	2	0.087	0.668	$8.1 \cdot 10^3$
3	0.149	$1.2 \cdot 10^5$	3	0.014	1.617	$3.3 \cdot 10^6$
4	0.501	$2.4 \cdot 10^7$	4	0.070	2.140	$1.8 \cdot 10^8$
5	1.568	$2.5 \cdot 10^8$	5	0.301	1.734	$1.3 \cdot 10^9$
			6	0.857	3.611	$9.7 \cdot 10^9$
			7	1.555	5.120	$7.2 \cdot 10^{11}$

Notes. For EDT-10: $c_3 = 10.5 \text{ MPa}^{-1}$; $E = 3200 \text{ MPa}$; $G = 1250 \text{ MPa}$; $c_m = 0.250 \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$. For polycarbonate: $A = 1/2G = 4.42 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$; $B = 1/2G^2 = 3.91 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ MPa}^{-2}$; $E = 3054 \text{ MPa}$; $G = 1131 \text{ MPa}$; $c_{1m} = 0.200 \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$; $c_{3m} = 0.125 \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$. The elasticity and shear moduli are determined at 20°C .

Let Eq.(5) take the form

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{11}(t, T) &= \frac{\sigma_{11}}{E} \left[1 + F_1(t, T) \right] + \frac{\sigma_{11}^3}{E^2} F_3(t, T); \\ \varepsilon_{12}(t, T) &= A \sigma_{12} \left[1 + F_1(t, T) \right] + B \sigma_{12}^3 F_3(t, T), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $A = 1/2G$ and $B = 1/2G^2$. $F_1(t, T) \neq F_3(t, T)$ are time and temperature functions of the linear and nonlinear components of the total creep deformation according to Eq.(4). In order to determine all unknown parameters, the data obtained from testing the polycarbonate in creep at two levels of shear stresses and at temperatures ranging

from 20 to 100 °C were used. Experimental curves and the results of their approximation are presented in Figure 2.

It is more convenient that a nonlinear component is expressed in the following way: if shear creep (6) is presented in values of compliance

$$I(t,T) = A [1 + F_1(t,T)] + B \sigma_{12}^2 F_3(t,T) \tag{7}$$

then using the test data of two various stress values, σ_{12I} and σ_{12II} Eq.(7) yields

$$I_I(t,T) - I_{II}(t,T) = B F_3(t,T)(\sigma_{12I}^2 - \sigma_{12II}^2) ,$$

and consequently
$$F_3(t,T) = \frac{I_I(t,T) - I_{II}(t,T)}{B(\sigma_{12I}^2 - \sigma_{12II}^2)} .$$

The treatment of the test data in this way allows us to approximate the data and define separately parameters of the function $F_1(t,T)$ and $F_3(t,T)$ by minimising some efficiency function, say, in the form of a mean square relative inaccuracy (Table 2). A basic difference between functions $\ln a_{m1} = c_{m1}(T - T_0)$ and $\ln a_{m3} = c_{m3}(T - T_0)$ of the polycarbonate should be marked. Hence, in view of Eq.(2) and with all the thermally rheological characteristics of deformation present, and on the condition that at each random constant temperature of the studied range the stress work W reaches its critical value $W^R(T)$ according to Eq.(1), the long term strength of both materials can be predicted.

In order to verify suitability of the approach discussed, the data on the long-term strength of binder EDT-10 and polycarbonate tested at various ranges of constant temperatures under conditions of creep in tension and disclosed in [5,6] were used as control data. According to Eqs.(1),(2),(5),(6) and the given conditions, we shall write

Figure 3. Long-term strength curves of EDT-10.

Figure 4. Long-term strength curves of polycarbonate.

for binder EDT-10:

$$W^R(T) = \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{2E} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{E} + \frac{c_3 \sigma_{11}^4}{E^2} \right) F_c(t, T) ; \quad (8)$$

and for the polycarbonate:

$$W^R(T) = \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{2E} + \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{E} F_1(t, T) + \frac{\sigma_{11}^4}{E^2} F_3(t, T) . \quad (9)$$

Using the characteristics given in Table 1 and 2, the equations are solved, and, with regard to ultimate stresses, curves of the long-term strength of both materials are calculated. It can be seen from Figure 3 and Figure 4 that, irrespectively of a relatively large scattering of the test data, which is common for long-term tests in general, the prediction reliability in the studied range of time can be estimated as satisfactory.

The examples given show that the long-term strength of materials whose failure is provoked basically by accumulation of viscoelastic strains can be estimated in an ample range of temperatures by employing the laws defining the long-term deformation of a material up to its failure and using certain strength criteria.

REFERENCES

1. Urzhumtsev Yu. S., Maksimov R. D., *Prediction of the Deformation of Polymeric Materials*, Riga, 1975, 416 p. (in Russian).
2. Tarnopol'sky Yu. M., Skudra A. M., *Structural Strength and Deformability of Fibreglass Plastics*, Riga, 1966, 260 p. (in Russian).
3. Skudra A. M., Bulavs F. J., Rocens K. A., *Creep and Static Fatigue of Reinforced Plastics*, Riga, 1971, 238 p. (in Russian).
4. Malmeister A. A., Janson J. O. *Predicting the Relaxation Properties of EDT-10 Epoxy Binder in the Complex Stressed State*, Mechanics of Composite Materials, Vol. 19, No. 5, 1983, pp. 663-667.
5. Adamovich A. G. *Temperature-Time Relationship of the Strength of Epoxy Resin EDT-10*, Polymer Mechanics, Vol. 14, No. 5, 1978, pp. 745-747.
6. *Polycarbonates in Machine-Building*, Ed. by Kestelman V. N., Mocsow, Mashinostroenie, 1971, 174 p. (in Russian).

SPACE APPLICATIONS

